

the mean. F_1 values for grain width, thickness, and weight were higher than in the mid-parent; F_2 values were toward the high parent.

Path coefficients showing direct and indirect effects of grain length, width, and thickness on grain weight and total correlations are presented in Table 2. There were no significant correlations among grain length, width, thickness, and weight in parents P. Basmati and IR1469. In Paizam 242, the association between length and thickness was positive, that between thickness and weight was negative. In P. Basmati, the direct effect of grain length on weight was positive and independent of indirect effects. In IR1469, the direct effect of grain length was negative and independent of indirect effects. In Paizam 242, the direct effect of thickness was negative and its indirect effect on grain length was high.

In the F_1 of P. Basmati/IR1469, the associations among length and width and grain weight were positive. The high direct effect of width was influenced to some extent by the negative effect of grain length. In the F_1 of P. Basmat/Paizam 242, there were no significant associations among the four characters.

Correlations in F_2 populations showed similar trends. Associations

Table 2. Path coefficients for components of 100-grain weight. CRRI, India, 1988.

Influence and association	Parents			F_1		F_2	
	Pakistan Basmati	IR1469	Paizam 242	Pakistan Basmati/IR1469	Pakistan Basmati/Paizam 242	Pakistan Basmati/IR1469	Pakistan Basmati/Paizam 242
<i>100-grain weight vs grain length</i>							
Direct effect	0.3805	-0.7134	0.1822	-0.2860	0.1434	0.4876	0.3636
Indirect effect via grain width	0.0913	0.0838	0.0088	0.7195	0.2372	-0.0314	-0.0155
Indirect effect via thickness	-0.0250	0.0949	-0.6349	0.0977	-0.0572	0.0664	0.0903
Total correlation	0.4468	-0.5347	-0.4439	0.5312	0.3234	0.5226**	0.4384**
<i>100-grain weight vs grain width</i>							
Direct effect	0.2269	0.2260	0.0915	0.8342	0.4997	0.4097	0.3262
Indirect effect via grain length	0.1531	-0.2645	0.0176	-0.2466	0.0681	-0.0374	-0.0172
Indirect effect via grain thickness	-0.0116	0.1087	0.0850	0.0855	-0.0370	0.1592	0.1795
Total correlation	0.3684	0.0702	0.1941	0.6731**	0.5308	0.5315**	0.4885**
<i>100-grain weight vs grain thickness</i>							
Direct effect	-0.0807	-0.3531	-0.7598	0.1789	-0.2148	0.2451	0.3178
Indirect effect via grain length	0.1177	0.1917	0.1522	-0.1563	0.0382	0.1321	0.1033
Indirect effect via grain width	0.0325	-0.0696	-0.0102	0.3989	0.0861	0.2661	0.1843
Total correlation	0.0695	-0.2310	-0.6178**	0.4215	-0.0905	0.6433**	0.6054**

among all characters except grain length and width were positive. The direct effects of grain length and width were positive. The direct effect of grain length and width on weight were equal. The direct effect of grain length was independent of indirect effects. Grain width was influenced by the indirect effect of grain thickness. The direct effect of grain thickness was due primarily to the indirect effects of grain

length and grain width.

Inheritance of grain length and width were found to be independent and governed by different sets of genes. Grain thickness depends on the correlation of length and width. With the independent action of length and width, grain weight can exceed both parents. Inheritance patterns of grain dimensions are useful in breeding for a specific grain type. □

Disease resistance

Disease resistance in Chinese hybrid rices

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More than 10 new hybrid rices are developed in China each year. Breeders have been focusing on yield characters. We report on the disease resistance of the hybrid rices involved in the 1987-88 regional test in South China and Jiangxi Province.

Pyricularia oryzae mixed with many monoconidial isolates from Jiangxi (suspension = 50-60 conidial 100 parts) was spray inoculated at the seedling stage. *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* from highly virulent group XII was inoculated by

cutting flag leaves during heading. We also evaluated the incidence of blast (Bl), bacterial blight (BB), sheath blight (ShB), and false smut (FS).

More of 87 hybrid cultivars tested in 1987 and 1988 were resistant to Bl than to BB (see table). Cultivar

Distribution, by resistance, of hybrid rices tested in Jiangxi, China, 1987-88.

Year	Disease	Cultivars showing given disease reaction										Resistant cultivars (%)	
		R		MR		MS		S		HS			Cultivars (no.)
		no.	%	no.	%	no.	%	no.	%	no.	%		
1987	Bl	4	8.7	15	32.6	19	41.3	5	10.9	3	6.5	46	41.3
	BB	2	4.4	5	11.1	12	26.7	8	17.8	18	40.0	45	15.5
1988	Bl	20	52.6	9	23.7	5	13.2	4	10.5	0	0	38	76.3
	BB	1	2.4	2	4.8	1	2.4	9	21.4	29	69.1	42	7.0

reactions to BI followed an almost normal distribution; in reactions to BB, susceptible types MS, S, and HS prevailed. BI-resistant types MR and R (76.31%) dominated in 1988 because almost half the resistant combinations were derived from Minghui 63, a

resistant R-line.

Most of the 20 hybrids tested both years were resistant to BI. All combinations from A-lines and all R-lines except Xiuhui 2, Ce 49, and Pinghui 3 were susceptible to BB. Disease severity by inoculation was

consistent with that in the plots. Most hybrids were susceptible to FS in at least 1 yr and in a plot.

Disease resistance in hybrid rice is determined by the parents. A-lines currently available are not resistant. □

Changes in total phenols in rice varieties inoculated with *Rhizoctonia solani* and treated with carbendazim

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We inoculated rice varieties ADT31, CR1009, AU42/1, IR20, and White Ponni with *R. solani* at maximum tillering (80 d old) by single sclerotium method in an experiment during 1985 samba season (Aug-Jan). Fungicide (0.1 % carbendazim) was sprayed 3 d after inoculation (DAI). Portions of the plant sheath were sampled 3, 5, and 7 DAI and 3, 5, and 7 d after fungicide application and analyzed for changes in total phenolic content.

Changes in total phenolics after *R. solani* inoculation and carbendazim application. Annamalai University, India, 1985.

Days after inoculation and fungicide application	Treatment	Total phenolic content ^a					
		ADT31	CR1009	AU42/1	IR20	White ponni	Mean
3	Healthy	2.89	3.07	3.02	3.10	3.04	3.02
	Inoculated	3.17	3.26	3.19	3.25	3.18	3.21
	Fungicide treated	3.68	3.88	3.85	3.92	3.76	3.82
5	Healthy	2.78	2.95	2.87	2.94	2.88	2.88
	Inoculated	3.01	3.13	3.08	3.16	3.05	3.09
	Fungicide treated	3.48	3.68	3.56	3.71	3.59	3.60
7	Healthy	2.68	2.78	2.78	2.87	2.74	2.79
	Inoculated	2.84	3.04	2.92	3.02	2.85	2.93
	Fungicide treated	3.23	3.37	3.18	3.30	3.12	3.24

^a In mg/g of tissue on dry weight basis in catechol equivalent.

Highly susceptible ADT31 contained less total phenols than susceptible CR1009, AU42/1, IR20, and White Ponni (see table). Total

phenolic content in all varieties increased with *R. solani* inoculation and with fungicide application, but decreased with plant age. □

Conditions for sporulation of rice blast (BI) fungus

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We studied the effects of 17 media and 3 irradiation levels on sporulation of 41 isolates of rice BI fungus (*Pyricularia oryzae*) during 1986-87. All isolates were grown on yeast starch agar and kept in an incubator at 28 °C.

Cultures were irradiated continuously at a distance of 30 cm from the lamp.

Test tubes containing 5 ml each of different media were inoculated by putting a 3 mm² piece of mycelial agar

Table 1. Effect of growth medium on sporulation of rice BI fungus. Hangzhou, China, 1987.

Medium	Mean sporulation ^a (10 ⁴ conidia/ml)
Cornmeal rice straw agar	(40, 50, 20) ^b 27.89 a
Rice leaf potato agar	(100, 200, 20) ^c 11.93 b
Rice straw agar	(100, 20) ^c 11.91 b
Oatmeal agar	(40, 20) 10.68 c
Cornmeal agar	(50, 20) 9.46 d
Corn leaf potato agar	(100, 200, 20) ^c 9.23 d
Rice bran rice leaf agar	(20, 50, 20) 8.85 d
Rice leaf agar	(100, 20) ^d 7.83 e
Rice bran agar	(20, 20) 5.94 f
Rice polish agar	(20, 20) 5.61 fg
Cornmeal beef extract agar	(40, 40, 20) ^d 5.13 gh
Prune agar	(1, 20) ^e 4.48 hi
Yeast starch agar	(2, 10, 20) 4.26 i
Barley agar	(50, 20) ^c 3.51 j
Potato agar	(200, 20) 3.13 j
V-8 juice rice straw agar	(250, 50, 20) ^f 2.89 j
Protein peptone yeast agar	(10, 5, 20) 1.45 k

^a Av of 2 replications of 41 isolates. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 1% level by DMRT. ^b Contains 40 g cornmeal, 50 g rice straw, 20 g agar, 1000 ml distilled water. ^c Plus 20 g sucrose. ^d Plus 10 g glucose. ^e 1 g lactose, 1 g yeast extract. ^f Plus 3 g CaCO₃.